

Fig. 1
Detail from Antonio
Francesco Lucini (after
Matteo Perez d'Aleccio),
*Disegni della guerra, assedio
et assalti dati dall'armata
turchesca all'isola di Malta
l'anno MDLXV[...]*,
engraving, 1631.
(Courtesy of Bibliothèque
nationale de France,
département Cartes et plans /
Source: BnF, GE BB-246)

A Story of Veneration and Preservation

The Seventeenth-Century Marian Paintings of the Old Parish Church of Mqabba

Having lost their original setting, Jonathan Farrugia traces the story of the still-surviving Marian altarpieces preserved at the Mqabba parish church, and adds a sixth painting, previously assumed lost, now held in a private collection

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Over the past five years, significant efforts have been made to conserve several seventeenth-century paintings of the Virgin Mary belonging to the parish church of Mqabba. It is believed that these altarpieces are the work of vernacular artists,¹ while being charming in their own way. These conservation projects were accompanied by a thorough examination of documentary sources to properly contextualise the artworks.² This required an in-depth study of records from the pastoral visitations conducted between 1575 and 1699, a period concluding with the completion of the current church. As a result, several paintings still held by the parish were accurately dated.

Fig. 2
The Holy Family with St Basil and St Roque, oil on canvas, 1677, Church of St Basil, Mqabba, after the recent conservation intervention by PrevArti. (Photo: Ian Noel Pace)

The sources and the context

Mqabba was established as an autonomous parish on 15 September 1598, under the patronage of the Assumption of the Virgin. The written records for this study begin with the pastoral visitation conducted by Mgr Dusina in 1575, which provides the first details of the churches in the village and the images they possessed. Additional sources include the notes from subsequent pastoral visitations, which offer further insights into the movable property of the churches throughout the first century of

opposite: Figs 3-4
The Assumption of the Virgin or The Coronation of the Virgin, oil on canvas, pre-1654, before and after restoration treatments carried out by Sabine Azzopardi in 2018. (Courtesy of Sabine Azzopardi)

the parish's existence, up until the pastoral visitation by Bishop Cocco Palmieri in 1699. By then the new church had been completed.

When Dusina visited *Casale Michabebe* on 8 February 1575, he found eight small churches: St Basil, St Michael the Archangel, St Catherine of Alexandria, St Peter, the Annunciation, the Visitation, and two dedicated to the Assumption. Within some years, several of these churches would cease to exist, including the Assumption and Visitation churches, which were replaced by the construction of the original parish church, completed around 1607. The earliest pastoral records indicate that some churches featured wooden icons or wall paintings on their main altars.³

The records also provide valuable information about the development of the main parish church. Initially, it housed five altars: two dedicated to the Assumption, and single altars dedicated to Our Lady of the Rosary, the Immaculate Conception, and the Annunciation. By the mid-seventeenth century, two additional altars, dedicated to the Visitation and the Holy Spirit, were added. The paintings on all of these altars, in one form or another, depicted the Virgin Mary.

The Marian themes in the filial churches

Throughout the seventeenth century, all six of the existing churches featured Marian imagery. Four of these churches were not dedicated to the Virgin Mary, yet her presence was still central in their main paintings.

In many cases, these paintings depicted the popular image of the Virgin holding her divine child. From the earliest records following the foundation of the parish, we know that the Church of St Basil originally housed a

wooden triptych, with the Virgin at the centre, flanked by St Basil and St Joseph.⁴ The only painting in the Church of St Catherine depicted the Blessed Virgin with St Peter and the titular saint.⁵ Shortly thereafter, this was replaced by a new painting showing the Virgin with Child in the upper register, and St Catherine and St Andrew in the lower.⁶ Meanwhile, a painting depicting Mary with St Michael the Archangel and St Jerome has been recorded in St Michael's Church since 1634.⁷

The Church of St Peter is reported to have had a painting featuring Mary in 1679, accompanied by St Peter and St Paul.⁸ In the same year, the new altarpiece for St Basil's Church was mentioned for the first time. Amongst a multitude of figures, the Virgin is depicted holding her breast and pouring out milk (Fig. 2).⁹

None of these paintings have survived, except for the titular painting of St Basil's Church, first mentioned in 1679. However, of the paintings once recorded in the old parish church, five are still in the parish's possession, and another painting, now in a private collection, has been identified as a likely candidate for one of these lost works.

The painting of the *Assumption and the Coronation of the Virgin*

During a visit on 9 December 1615, Bishop Baldassare Cagliares noted that the newly constructed parish church had two altars dedicated to the Assumption of the Virgin: the main altar and another located to its right.¹⁰ The earliest description of this second altar dates to 1634, when Bishop Pontremoli recorded in his minutes that it featured a painting of the Virgin's Assumption into heaven.¹¹

A more detailed account comes from the pastoral visit conducted by Bishop Balaguer on 16 January 1654. He described the painting as depicting the *Assumption of the Virgin with St Joseph and St Catherine*.¹² The absence of the saints in earlier descriptions suggests that this was a new painting, one that remains on the same altar to this day.

During Bishop Molina's visit in 1679, the depiction of the Holy Trinity crowning Mary was mentioned for the first time.¹³ This suggests that, over the preceding twenty-five years, the altar's dedication may have shifted from the *Assumption* to the *Coronation of Mary*. Whether the Holy Trinity was a later addition remains unclear (Figs 3-4).

opposite: Fig. 5
Detail from the IR imagery of *The Immaculate Conception*, revealing parts of the underpainting. (Photo: David Bugeja)

Fig. 6
The Immaculate Conception, oil on canvas, pre-1686, after restoration treatment carried out by Sabine Azzopardi in 2019. (Courtesy of Sabine Azzopardi)

original, the vernacular painter who made the addition overpainted the entire lower part in a sombre dark colour. This obscured many details, including the broken wheel associated with St Catherine and much of the exquisite countryside in the background, both of which were uncovered during the conservation process.

The painting of *Our Lady del Soccorso* and *The Immaculate Conception*

The earliest reference to the devotion to the Immaculate Conception of Mary in Mqabba dates back to 1615, when the first parish church, then dedicated to the Assumption, included an altar with an *icona decens*¹⁵ pointing to this emerging devotion. By 1630, the altar was described as *sub invocatio[n]e della concep[tio]ne: B.V. del Soccorso*,¹⁶ with its painting noted as an *iconam pulcram referentem Beata Virgine del Soccorso*.¹⁷

For over fifty years, no further changes to the altar were recorded. However, during the pastoral visit of 1686, Bishop Cocco Palmieri documented a return to the original dedication: *sub titulo Conceptionis B.M. Virginis*.¹⁸ The altar now featured a newly painted canvas depicting the *Immaculate Conception with St Anne* (Fig. 6).¹⁹

This painting underwent some modifications over time but remained in place until 1942, when the altar was destroyed during the infamous bombing of 9 April. Fortunately, the painting survived, though it was severely damaged. Upon the rebuilding of the church's transept, it was replaced by a painting of lesser quality, commissioned from Cleto Luzzi.

The painting was kept for years in a storage room, partially concealed behind a closet, until it was displayed in the church on the 75th anniversary of the bombing. In

The restoration work conducted on this painting in 2018 did not indicate that the figures were added at a later stage. However, if they were painted twenty years after the original composition, it would not be surprising if the difference in age went undetected. One clue supporting this possibility is the cramped arrangement of the figures. Without the addition of God the Father and Christ, the composition would appear more spacious, aligning unmistakably with the theme of the Assumption, as the space they occupy could easily have been filled with clouds and light, remnants of which are still visible.

Bishop Cocco Palmieri visited the church in 1693 and noted that this painting was displayed on a newly built altar in the completed section of the new church, indicating that it had found its permanent placement, where it remains to this day.¹⁴

The recent restoration work revealed that another section had been added to the bottom of the painting, likely to accommodate the new and larger stone frame. This alteration led to the absurd elongation of the saints' figures, resulting in disproportionate and rough feet, and the inclusion of horrendous souls in purgatory in the space between them. To integrate the new section with the

opposite, top: Figs 7-8
The Annunciation of the Virgin, oil on canvas, pre-1621, before and after restoration treatments. The restoration was carried out by Atelier del Restauro in 2021.
 (Courtesy of Atelier del Restauro)

opposite, below: Figs 9-10
The Visitation of Mary to Elizabeth, oil on canvas, pre-1654, before and after restoration treatments. The restoration was carried out by Amy Sciberras in 2023.
 (Courtesy of Amy Sciberras – ASC Conservation Centre Ltd / Photo: Manuel Ciantar and Suzanne Ciantar Ferrito)

2019, it was restored to its original splendour, and infrared photographic analysis revealed that the painting had been created over an earlier image (Fig. 5). The underlying composition is most likely that of the *Madonna del Soccorso*, referenced in all pastoral visitation reports between 1630 and 1686. From the little that can be seen in the infrared photographs, it is evident that in the original image the Virgin's mantle was not swirling around her, the palms of her hands were pressed together in prayer, while the crescent moon beneath her feet was pointing upwards; it can thus be concluded that the artist who composed the painting, as seen today, developed a similar theme to the original. Among the five surviving seventeenth-century paintings in Mqabba, this work is undoubtedly the finest, standing as one of the earliest examples of baroque art in the church.

The painting of *The Annunciation*

Another surviving painting from this period is that of the *Annunciation of the Virgin* (Fig. 7), which is currently housed in the 'old' sacristy of the church. Originally, a small church dedicated to this event existed, though it was demolished by the end of the sixteenth century. The first parish church, however, included an altar dedicated to the Annunciation as soon as it was completed. Initially, the altar had no painting, but by 1621, a notable image depicting this episode was recorded.²⁰

The painting remained in the church until just before 1693, when the transept of the new parish church was completed, and the altar was rededicated with a new painting of *The Holy Crucifix*.²¹ This shift had been anticipated for some time, as in 1674, the Sodalità degli Agonizzanti was established at this altar, and a large crucifix was placed in front of the *Annunciation* painting.

For centuries, the painting was left in the sacristy, where it suffered some tears. It was restored in 2021 (Fig. 8), revealing fascinating details in the architectural design of the setting for the angelic visit. The painting may also represent one of the earliest examples of single-point perspective in Maltese vernacular art.²²

The painting of *The Visitation*

Until 1635, only five altars were mentioned in the new parish church: the main altar and four others located in the transepts. The church also had a short nave, which later housed two additional altars.

The first of these altars to be mentioned is that of the *Visitation of the Virgin to Elizabeth*, which recalled the earlier church dedicated to this event that once stood on the same site as the first parish church. Due to popular devotion, this altar was erected in 1635,²³ though no reference to a painting is made until 1654.²⁴ During his visit, the bishop noted that the altar featured a painting depicting the *Visitation* (Figs 9-10), but without specifying whether it was a new acquisition. The style of the painting is notably old-fashioned, even by rural standards. In fact, the same visitation records the first mention of the *Assumption* or *Coronation* painting, which was executed in a more refined style.

The Visitation was eventually replaced with a new one after the nave of the new church was completed. For centuries, the original painting was stored, presumably in the 'old' sacristy, and later moved to the newly built sacristy after the war.

Restoration work carried out in 2023 revealed that while the painting had undergone previous interventions, it had not suffered significant damage (Fig. 10).

Fig. 11
The Descent of the Holy Spirit, oil on canvas, 1637. Awaiting restoration.
 (Photo: Ian Noel Pace)

The painting of *The Descent of the Holy Spirit*

The final painting from this period, and still in the parish's possession, represents the *Descent of the Holy Spirit* (Fig. 11). Mary is the central figure, surrounded by the apostles, each with a small tongue of fire above their heads. Dated 1637, the painting includes a note indicating that it was created as an *ex voto*. As a result, it is first mentioned in the pastoral visitation of 1646, which records that the altar had been recently constructed.²⁵ The painting remained in its original location until sometime after the completion of the new church in 1699, when it was replaced by a new work commissioned to fit the cross-shaped stone cornice of the newly built altar.

For many years, the painting was kept in a storage room where it suffered considerable damage. Restoration and conservation are planned for the near future. X-ray photographic analysis has revealed that much of the painting has been overpainted, likely due to previous losses or changing artistic tastes.

The painting of *Our Lady of the Rosary*

An altar that was consistently present in the church, always adorned with a painting, was that dedicated to Our Lady of the Rosary. The altar painting featured depictions of the fifteen mysteries. Around 1686, a new painting was commissioned, featuring St Dominic, St Catherine of Siena, King David, and St Rosa of Lima in the lower register.²⁶ This painting was replaced in 1893 by a work by Giuseppe Cali, though the reason for the replacement remains unknown.

In recent years, through my contacts with various art collectors, a surviving fragment of this painting has

possibly been identified. Based on first-hand accounts, I know that, to raise funds for rebuilding the damaged churches, several parish priests unfortunately resorted to selling artefacts that were no longer in use after being replaced. Some of the individuals who purchased these artefacts kept records of their provenance. A few years ago, I was contacted by a collector who had bought a painting depicting the *Virgin and Child with the Rosary*. The painting had been purchased from the heirs of a renowned collector who had acquired many items from churches, and the notes indicated that the painting came from Mqabba.

While the canvas now only depicts the *Virgin and Child* (Fig. 12), it is evident that the Christ-Child is handing his rosary to a figure who was likely part of a lower register that is now lost. After careful analysis, including consideration of the fifteen mysteries of the rosary originally painted around the perimeter and the four figures in the lower register, the size and composition of the painting seem to align well with the 1686 painting. It is, therefore, likely a fragment of the earlier work.

Conclusion

The ongoing conservation projects in Mqabba exemplify the dual objectives of preserving artistic heritage and

Fig. 12
The Virgin of the Rosary, oil on canvas, c.1686.
 (Private Collection, Malta / Photo: Ian Noel Pace)

deepening historical understanding. By coupling meticulous restoration with rigorous archival research, these efforts have brought new clarity to the history of the village's Marian paintings. The accurate dating of previously misattributed works, the rediscovery of lost or forgotten pieces, and the uncovering of hidden details have enriched the narrative of Mqabba's devotional and artistic life.

These achievements not only safeguard the legacy of a rural parish but also invite renewed appreciation from locals and visitors alike. As the remaining projects unfold, the hope is that these remarkable artefacts will continue to inspire devotion and admiration for generations to come.

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Notes

1 The only possible exception, according to restorer Sabine Azzopardi, is the original part of the *Coronation of the Virgin*,

which could have been the work of an Italian artist, or with Italian affiliations.

- 2 The conservation works were entrusted to Ms Sabine Azzopardi (*The Coronation of the Virgin*, *The Immaculate Conception*), the Atelier del Restauro (*The Annunciation of the Virgin*), and Ms Amy Sciberras (*The Visitation of the Virgin*). The conservation of *The Descent of the Holy Spirit* will be entrusted to the Atelier del Restauro.
- 3 The churches of St Basil and the Annunciation had an *icona parva lignea* each; St Catherine had a presumably larger *icona lignea*; the church of the Assumption, located adjacent to the church of the Annunciation, had *figuris in pariete depictis*. AAM [Archivium Archiepiscopali Melitensis], *Visitatio Duzzina*, 1575, ff. 121-122.
- 4 AAM, *Visitatio Cagliares*, 1615, f. 238v.
- 5 *Ibid.*, f. 237v.
- 6 In 1630 (AAM, *Visitatio Cagliares*, f. 66v), the painting is reported as showing St Catherine and St Andrew, with no mention of the Virgin, then from 1634 (AAM, *Visitatio Pontremoli*, 1634, f. 65r) the Virgin is described as *de monte Carmelo*, but later the title is no longer specified.
- 7 AAM, *Visitatio Pontremoli*, 1634, f. 66r.
- 8 AAM, *Visitatio Molina*, 1679, f. 263r. In earlier records the painting is described as containing the Holy Trinity, St Peter and St Agatha or St Anastasia.
- 9 *Ibid.*, f. 263v.
- 10 AAM, *Visitatio Cagliares*, 1615, f. 236r.
- 11 AAM, *Visitatio Pontremoli*, 1634, f. 64r.
- 12 AAM, *Visitatio Balaguer*, 1654, f. 235r.
- 13 AAM, *Visitatio Molina*, 1679, f. 259r.
- 14 AAM, *Visitatio Cocco Palmieri*, 1693, f. 107v.
- 15 'Decent image'. AAM, *Visitatio Cagliares*, 1615, f. 237r.
- 16 'Under the invocation of the conception of the Blessed Virgin of Mercy'.
- 17 'Beautiful icon referring to the Blessed Virgin of Mercy'. AAM, *Visitatio Cagliares*, 1630, f. 66r.
- 18 'Under the title of the Conception of the Blessed Virgin Mary'.
- 19 AAM, *Visitatio Cocco Palmieri*, 1686, f. 224r-v.
- 20 AAM, *Visitatio Cagliares*, 1621, f. 89v.
- 21 AAM, *Visitatio Cocco Palmieri*, 1693, f. 109r.
- 22 Mario Buhagiar and Keith Sciberras, 'Three Early Seventeenth-Century Vernacular Paintings at Imqabba', *Melita Historica*, Vol. 11 No. 1 (1992), 31.
- 23 AAM, *Visitatio Balaguer*, 1635, f. 108v.
- 24 AAM, *Visitatio Balaguer*, 1654, f. 235v.
- 25 AAM *Visitatio Balaguer*, 1646, f. 144r.
- 26 AAM, *Visitatio Cocco Palmieri*, 1686, f. 223r.